

Simple Neuron Circuit with Adjustable Weights and its Application to Neural Based ADC

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Abstract— A neuron circuit design whose weights can be changed even after the fabrication is presented here. It is based on modified CMOS inverter synapses. Weights can be modified by changing the threshold voltage of the inverters. The application of this neuron model circuit design for the analog to digital converter has been implemented. The implementation has been done using CADENCE software VIRTUOSO tool using the 180 nm process technology for 1.8 V.

Index Terms—neuromorphic circuit design, analog VLSI, ADC.

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENTLY there have been many implementations of the various neuron models starting from the simple formal neuron models [1] to the latest spiking neuron model based on mathematical equations [2], [3]. These implementations have been done keeping in mind to build some day a *neuro-computer* capable to perform the functions as that of the *Human Brain*. This trend got momentum after the pioneering work of C. Mead [4].

However for the implementation of the weights these neuron circuits use the Floating gate MOS transistors where the capacitance of the floating gate is used for weights. The poly silicon is used as capacitance in these Floating Gate MOS, so it requires larger area on the chip [5]. Also there has been implementation using the resistors for the weights [6]. But here also the weights once fabricated cannot be changed. Also the values are fixed after the fabrication process. C.K. Pham implemented the synapse circuits using the resistors. This circuit requires huge area because of the presence of resistors and the weights were fixed after the fabrication of the chip. So there is a need for less area and adjustable weight neuron circuit which is proposed in this paper. Since this neuron circuit is based on the simple formal model of the neuron it cannot be used to implement the neuro-computer rather can be used to realize the neural analog circuits because of its simplicity & less area required. We

suggest for the realization of neuro-computer spiking neuron model circuits should be used since they perfectly mimic the behavior of the human brain.

The neural networks have been even used to implement the neural based analog circuits like the filter design, analog multiplier, integrator and the ADC [7], [8], [9], [10]. For the implementation of the filter Rodriguez et al [11] used the floating gate MOS transistors. These circuits require large area because of the implementation of the capacitance using poly silicon floating gate capacitors. Also there have been few implementations of the neural based Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) [12], [13], [14]. These most implementations have been done using the symmetrical connections of the Hopfield Network. These circuits are highly complex and require huge hardware. Avitabile et al. [15] presented a class of neural networks with the nonsymmetrical connections in contrast to the Hopfield network.

The implementation of feed-forward and nonsymmetrical network is reported by Mamoru. T et al. in [16]. Here the weights of the synapse were fixed by the value of the channel conductances of the MOS transistors. Also C. K. Pham implemented the ADC using the inverters but the presence of resistors made the circuit bulky. In this paper we have implemented the circuit for the ADC using our proposed neuron circuit. It requires less area and also the accuracy is better.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II we have introduced the variable threshold CMOS inverter which is used for the neuron circuit model implementation. In Section III presents the modified novel neuron model circuits, where we can change the weights of the synapses using the control voltage V_c . In Section IV 3-bit neural based ADC is analyzed and implemented using the novel neural model presented. In Section V simulation results have been presented using the CADENCE software for 180 nm process technology. Finally in Section VI conclusions are drawn.

II. ADJUSTABLE THRESHOLD CMOS INVERTER

The transconductance K is fixed by the process parameters and the W/L ratio of the MOS transistors. The threshold voltage is determined by this K ratio in the CMOS inverters. The K is given by

$$K = \mu C_{ox} \frac{W}{L} \quad (1)$$

Manuscript received February 10, 2012.

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inverter.

From left the first 3 modified inverters are the synapses and the later 2 inverters are the Decision Making Amplifier which acts as the implementation of Hard – Limiting Threshold Function. The threshold of this inverter can be varied by changing the Vc voltage.

The common voltage Vout is determined when the current (in) flowing through the NMOS is equal to the current (ip) flowing in NMOS transistors

The parallel conductance of all the NMOS is gn+gn' and all PMOS is gp then the vout is given by

$$V_{out} = \frac{i_n}{g_n} \tag{6}$$

Then in and ip are given by

$$i_n = \sum_{j=1}^n T_j V_j \tag{7}$$

$$i_p = \sum_{j=1}^n T_j V_j' \tag{8}$$

The hard limiting threshold function is realized by the two cascaded CMOS inverters as

$$V_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sum_{j=1}^n T_j V_j \leq 1/2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \sum_{j=1}^n T_j V_j > 1/2 \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

Here in the above fig. (2) we have connected the control voltage Vc .By changing this control voltage we can change the weights of the synapses. Also the cascaded decision making inverters need to change their threshold to make correct decisions so we connected same control voltage Vc. Also for more flexibility we can give different voltage but unnecessarily will increase the number of pins.

IV. NEURAL BASED 3-BIT ADC

The 3 bit modified circuit of the Analog to Digital Converter is shown in the fig. (3). It consists of the 3 neuron circuits as presented in previous section. The decision making amplifier output is given to the extra connected CMOS inverter for converting the output logic to the positive logic.

Each neuron has the weights 4,2 & 1 respectively. The analog input is given to the CMOS inverter which has the weight 8. So every input to the neuron is either high or low level. The m can thus be given as

$$m = \frac{8 + \sum_1^3 T_j V_j}{8 + \sum_1^3 T_j V_j'} \tag{10}$$

The data is converted from MSB to LSB and the previous converted data are used for the next conversion.

By using the control voltage Vc, The threshold of the inverter can be tuned to get the optimized output of the neural

based 3-bit ADC.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the modified ADC.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

We have designed and simulated the neural based ADC in 180nm process technology in CADENCE. The input voltage to the circuit was 1.8 V. The analog input to the inverter is a triangular wave of 20nsec period with delay time of 0nsec and rise and fall time equal to the 1nsec each.

The modified CMOS inverter ratios were designed according to the weights needed and particularly the PMOS size was made 2.7 times greater than the NMOS to make the in and ip equal. The simulation results of the transient analysis for the period of 80nsec is shown in the fig (4).

Fig. 4 . Transient analysis output waveforms of the modified ADC.

VI. CONCLUSION

Neuron Circuit has been designed and presented here whose weights can be altered by the control voltage. Also the neural based 3-bit ADC has been successfully implemented using the proposed neuron model. This neuron circuit can be used to implement other neural based analog circuits.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Syed Muffassir M. S. Ali would like to thank Shoeb M.Khan of Hyundai Ltd for his support during this implementation.

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